

Original Article

Kinetics of Lymphocytes Reconstitution Post Allogeneic Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplantation: Two years of Follow-up

Eida Elmansorry

Department of Medical Laboratories, Faculty of Medical Technology, University of Tripoli, Libya

ARTICLE INFO

Corresponding Email. eidaelmansorry@yahoo.com

Received: 10-03-2022 **Accepted:** 21-03-2022 **Published:** 22-03-2022

Keywords: Allogeneic, Hematopoietic, Stem Cell, Transplantation.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

Background and aims. Allogeneic hematopoietic stem cells transplantation (HSCT) is strong curative treatment for several classes of immunodeficiency, metabolic disorders, and haematopoietic malignancies. Depending on HSCT procedure, thousands of patients could heal from their underlying disease. The ability of hematopoietic stem cells transplantation (HSCT) to cure is affected by variant factors. The objectives of this study were to analyze the kinetics of lymphocyte recovery at different time points after allogeneic hematopoietic stem cells transplantation and to correlate their recovery with some factors that influence the transplantation clinical outcome. **Methods.** In this study, 16 consecutive allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT) recipients were analysed during the first two-year post transplantation by measuring the absolute count of lymphocytes every three months for each patient. Data were presented as minimum, maximum and mean. **Results.** Frequencies of lymphocytes increased gradually during the first 24 months post HSCT and their recovery was affected by different factors such as graft source, patient age, and chronic graft versus host disease. Lymphocytes are essential for adaptive immune responses. Type of transplant, graft versus host disease, and recipient age affect their reconstitution. **Conclusion.** Proper lymphocyte recovery is associated with better clinical outcome and increased the survival rate.

Cite this article: Elmansorry E. Kinetics of Lymphocytes Reconstitution Post Allogeneic Hematopoietic Stem Cell

Transplantation: Two years of Follow-up. *Alq J Med App Sci.* 2022;5(1):166-171. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6374106>

INTRODUCTION

Allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT) is a curative treatment for patients with different malignant and non-malignant disorders; however, treatment efficacy is affected by variant factors include: the kind of disorder [1,2], state of disease before the transplant [3], stem cell source[4], human leucocytes antigens (HLA)-matching compatibility between the donor and recipient [5,6], conditioning regiments [7,8], cell removal [9,10], graft versus host disease (GVHD) and its treatment [11], and post-transplant infections [12,13]. Immune reconstitution after allogeneic Hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT) generates from the donor-derived progenitors and the proliferation of the immune cells transferred with the graft.

There is a significant difference in the kinetics of innate and adaptive immune recovery and the rapid reconstitution of monocytes and natural killer (NK) cells comparing with the delayed maturation of T and B lymphocytes, which may not complete until the first year after transplantation. Reconstitution of functional immune responses affected by many factors, particularly source of graft, graft versus host disease and/or its preventive therapy. Complete and functional recovery of both innate and adaptive immunity is necessary to limit the susceptibility to infection and to prevent relapse risk after allogeneic HSCT [14]. The Long defence insufficiency occurs mainly from deficiencies in effective cellular immune reconstitution [15-17].

Deficiency of B lymphocytes frequencies can be detected in few months post HSCT and influenced by chronic graft versus host disease (cGVHD) and / or its treatment [18-20]. Different kinds of procedures are performed to evaluate post-transplant immune recovery, including tests which done routinely in clinical laboratories (absolute lymphocytes counts, CD4+, CD8+, NK cells, B cells, and antibodies titers [21]. Recovery of lymphocytes from donor cells attack residual tumor cells early post transplantation and prevent relapse and thereby the absolute lymphocyte count serves as a predictor of the clinical outcome after HSCT [22]. Hence, this work was conducted to analyze kinetics of lymphocyte regeneration in 16 consecutive allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation recipients during two years of clinical follow-up, and

to compare their recovery according to different factors that affect transplantation outcome such as age of patient, chronic graft versus disease, and type of transplant.

METHODS

Study design and setting

An observational and descriptive study of patients undergoing allogeneic HSCT between January 2007 and January 2009 was carried out in laboratory of cellular therapy, Campus Virchow Clinic, Charite' University, Berlin, Germany. An ethical committee approval was taken from institutional ethical committee. Some patients received a myeloablative regimen, while others received a reduced-intensity regimen (depending on the underlying disorder) prior to allogeneic HSCT. All the recipients treated with Aciclovir as Antiviral prophylaxis and Anti Thymocytesglobulin, Cyclosporine-A, and Methotrexate as graft-versus-host disease (GVHD) prophylaxis. GVHD was defined as acute if it occurred before day 100 and chronic thereafter.

Data collection procedure

The study cohort comprised 16 consecutive patients who underwent allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT) with myeloablative or reduced-intensity conditioning. Patients receiving umbilical cord blood transplantation, or haplo-identical transplantation were excluded. Patients who died or relapsed were also excluded. The diagnosis they were referred to the hematopoietic stem cell transplantation unit for the following: Acute lymphoblastic leukemia, 38% (n=6); Acute myeloid Leukaemia, 25% (n=4); Wiscott-Aldrich syndrome, 13% (n=2); Fanconi Anemia, 6% (n=1); Chronic myeloid Leukaemia, 6% (n=1); severe combined immune deficiency, 6% (n=1); X-chromosomal Adrenoleukodystrophy, 6% (n=1). About 10(63%) patients were males and 6(37%) were females; age ranged from 6 months to 22 years. Age of donors ranged from 7-50 years. Graft source was 69% (n=11) bone marrow and 31% (n=5) Peripheral Blood stem cell (PBSC). All patients received their graft from matched unrelated donors. 88% of the patients (n=14) had acute graft versus host disease, range from grade I-II, and 69% (n= 11) had grade II of chronic graft versus host disease.

In patients underwent reduced-intensity conditioning transplantation, total donor chimerism was assessed from bone marrow aspirates. Genotyping was analysed by short tandem repeat typing using the ABI 310 Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Inc., Foster City, CA). Alleles specific to donor or recipient were used for chimerism identification.

Fresh whole blood specimens were collected during the first two years post transplantation. Patient's peripheral venous blood was collected into 10-ml Li-heparin/EDTA vacutainer Becton Dickinson (BD, USA) after written informed consent. The study protocol was approved by laboratory of cellular therapy, Campus Virchow Clinic, Charite' University, Berlin, Germany. The Absolute Lymphocyte counts at time point of the study were assessed from complete blood counts drawn as part of routine clinical investigation after transplantation. Absolute Lymphocyte count for every patient was quantified every three months during the first two years post-transplant.

Statistical analysis

Statistics (means, minimal, and maximal values) were used to describe patient baseline characteristics. Results were presented as mean values of Lymphocytes, and p-values. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 18. Student's *t*-test was used to ascertain the significance of differences between mean values of two continuous variables and confirmed by nonparametric Mann-Whitney test.

RESULTS

Reconstitution of Lymphocytes

To analyze the lymphocytes reconstitution kinetics in all 16 patients, absolute count of lymphocytes/ μ l was measured in whole blood every three months during two years of follow-up. Counts of lymphocytes were measured and presented as mean, minimal, and maximal values. Mean of the lymphocytes increased from 1084/ μ l at first three months to 6998/ μ l at 24 months.

Table 1. Lymphocytes / μ l during 24 months post allogeneic HSCT (Mean, Minimal-/ Maximal values)

Time post HSCT	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
Three months	1084	333	1994
Six months	1669	799	3049
Nine months	2242	766	5416
Twelve months	2889	799	7488
Fifteen months	3568	865	7585
Eighteen months	5894	875	7693
Twenty-four months	6998	921	7733

Impact of stem cell source on the Lymphocytes recovery:

Upon the correlation with the factors that affect the regeneration of lymphocytes after allogeneic haematopoietic stem cell transplantation, we had compared the impact of graft source on the kinetics of lymphocytes recovery (Figure 1). The recovery of lymphocytes over time was significantly higher in patients having received bone marrow (BM) than in those transplanted from peripheral blood stem cells (PBSC) ($P \leq 0.003$).

Figure 1. Impact of graft source on lymphocyte recovery

Impact of chronic GVHD (cGVHD) on the recovery of Lymphocytes:

The reconstitution of Lymphocytes over time was significantly higher in patients without chronic graft versus host disease than in those with symptoms of chronic graft versus host ($P = 0.007$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Impact of chronic GVHD on lymphocyte recovery

Impact of recipient-age on the recovery of Lymphocytes

The reconstitution of Lymphocytes over time was significantly higher in patients whoe aged < 15 years (P= 0.001). Their recovery was similar in both groups at 24 months (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Impact of patient age on lymphocyte recovery

DISCUSSION

Immune reconstitution has a major role in the clinical outcome after allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT). The donor lymphoid reconstitution is a potent surrogate of immune recovery and the rapid lymphocyte regeneration is associated with a survival support post HSCT [23-25]. Allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT) gives a unique chance to improve the evolution of immune regeneration. Potent immune development and defense against invading pathogens needs efficient lymphocytes recovery [26,27]. After HSCT, the major rules that are very serious for a successful transplantation include engraftment of the transplanted stem cells; inhibit graft versus host disease (GVHD) and regeneration of active lymphocytes [28].

Rapid lymphocytes regeneration post HSCT is necessary for the reaching these goals. The lymphocytes regeneration and maturation from hematopoietic stem cells occurs in the thymus and bone marrow. In their tissues, lymphoid progenitor cells rapidly proliferate and differentiate to mature cells with highly diverse receptor repertoire. These Naive cells can react with different types of antigens [29-31]. Lateness of immune recovery post HSCT was accompanied with high rate of infections and relapse [32-34]. Immune responses which mediated by lymphocytes is influenced by different factors include conditioning treatment, thymic impairment in the host, graft source, graft dose, T-cell depletion, donor-host disparity, acute and chronic graft-versus-host disease (GVHD) preventive treatment or therapy.

Different studies have focused on evaluating Lymphocyte frequencies post HSCT, as they play a major role in the improvement of the clinical outcome after HSCT. In this study, we investigated kinetics of lymphocyte recovery post allogeneic HSCT and evaluated the impact of different factors on their recovery. We have found that the reconstitution of lymphocytes increased gradually during the first two year after allogeneic HSCT and related with long-term survival. The impact of the graft source on lymphocyte regeneration has been previously described and bone marrow as the source of allograft was associated with a higher lymphocyte's recovery [35]. Absolute count of lymphocytes was significantly higher in patients without the occurrence of later episode of chronic GVHD. Furthermore, early lymphocytes recovery was better in the patients who aged < 15 years especially in the first eighteen months with low rate of infections and relapse [36].

The current study has evaluated matched unrelated HSCT and observed that higher lymphocyte counts were associated with better outcome, because of a higher survival rate, lower mortality rate, less relapse, and less severity of graft versus host disease (GVHD). Faster lymphocyte reconstitution after HSCT may be a sign of more rapid immune recovery, leading to fewer infections and deaths. Low post-transplantation lymphocyte counts have been associated with cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection as well as with elevated rate of death from CMV disease. [37].

CONCLUSION

The finding of this study evaluated kinetics of lymphocyte reconstitutions during two years after HSCT and suggested that the absolute lymphocyte count (ALC) early after HSCT may have significant prognostic values. Low ALC early post HSCT is associated with higher risk of non-relapse mortality and poor survival because of graft versus host disease and

infections. Furthermore, type of transplant, patient age, and chronic graft versus host disease have a significant impact on lymphocyte reconstitution at different time points after allogeneic HSCT.

Disclaimer

The article has not been previously presented or published, and is not part of a thesis project.

Conflict of Interest

All materials and instruments were provided by the Immunology laboratory, Campus Virchow Clinic, Charite' University, Berlin, Germany.

REFERENCES

1. Devine SM, Adkins DR, Khoury H, Brown RA, Vij R, Blum W, et al. Recent advances in allogeneic hematopoietic stem-cell transplantation. *J Lab Clin Med.* 2003; 141(1): 7–32.
2. Burnett AK, Eden OB. The treatment of acute leukaemia. *The Lancet.* 1997; 349(9047): 270–275.
3. Horowitz MM, Bortin MM. The role of registries in evaluating the results of bone marrow transplantation. In: Treleaven J (ed). *Bone Marrow Transplantation in Practice.* 1992. Churchill Livingstone: Edinburgh, pp 367–377.
4. Korbiling M, Anderlini P, Hematology TA. Peripheral blood stem cell versus bone marrow allotransplantation: does the source of hematopoietic stem cells matter? *Blood.* 2001; 98: 2900–2908.
5. Davies SM, Wagner JE, Shu XO, Blazar BR, Katsanis E, Orchard PJ, et al. Unrelated donor bone marrow transplantation for children with acute leukemia. *J Clin Oncol* 1997; 15(2): 557–565.
6. Gustafsson A, Remberger M, Winiarski J, Ringden O. Unrelated bone marrow transplantation in children: outcome and a comparison with sibling donor grafting. *Bone Marrow Transplant.* 2000; 25: 1059–1065.
7. Michallet M, Bilger K, Garban F, Attal M, Huyn A, Blaise D, et al. Allogeneic hematopoietic stem-cell transplantation after nonmyeloablative preparative regimens: impact of pretransplantation and post transplantation factors on outcome. *J Clin Oncol.* 2001; 19(14): 3340–3349.
8. Morecki S, Gelfand Y, Nagler A, Or R, Naparster E, Varadi G, et al. Immune reconstitution following allogeneic stem cell transplantation in recipients conditioned by low intensity vs. myeloablative regimen. *Bone Marrow Transplant.* 2001; 28(3): 243–249.
9. Ash RC, Horowitz MM, Gale RP, Bekkum DW, Casper JT, Henslee PJ, et al. Bone marrow transplantation from related donors other than HLA-identical siblings: effect of T cell depletion. *Bone Marrow Transplant.* 1991; 7(6): 443–452.
10. Gilmore MJ, Patterson J, Ivory K, Brenner MK, Graphakos S, Janossy G, et al. Standardization of T-cell depletion in HLA matched bone marrow transplantation. *Br J Haematol.* 1986; 64(1): 69–75.
11. McClave P, Bartsch G, Anasetti C, Ash R, Beatty P, Gajewski J, et al. Unrelated donor marrow transplantation therapy for chronic myelogenous leukemia: initial experience of the National Marrow Donor Program. *Blood.* 1993; 81(2): 543–550.
12. Hongeng S, Krance RA, Bowman LC, Srivastara DK, Cunningham JM, Horwitz EM, et al. Outcomes of transplantation with matched-sibling and unrelated-donor bone marrow in children with leukaemia. *Lancet.* 1997; 350(9080): 767–771.
13. Ochs L, Shu XO, Miller J, Enright H, Wagner J, Filipovich A, et al. Late infections after allogeneic bone marrow transplantations: comparison of incidence in related and unrelated donor transplant recipients. *Blood.* 1995; 86(10): 3979–3986.
14. Ruggeri L, Mancusi A, Capanni M, Urbani E, Carotti A, Aloisi T, et al. Donor natural killer cell allorecognition of missing self in haploidentical hematopoietic transplantation for acute myeloid leukemia: challenging its predictive value. *Blood.* 2007; 110(1):433-440.
15. Small TN, Avigan D, Dupont B, Smith K, Black P, Heller G, et al. Immune reconstitution following T-cell depleted bone marrow transplantation: effect of age and post transplant graft rejection prophylaxis. *Biol Blood Marrow Transplant.* 1997; 3(2): 65–75.
16. Small TN, Papadopoulos EB, Boulad F, Black P, Castro-Malaspina H, Childs BH, et al. Comparison of immune reconstitution after unrelated and related T-cell depleted bone marrow transplantation: effect of patient age and donor leukocyte infusions. *Blood.* 1999; 93(2): 467–480.
17. Storek J, Espino G, Dawson MA, Storer B, Flowers ME, Maloney DG, et al. Low B-cell and monocyte counts on day 80 are associated with high infection rates between days 100 and 365 after allogeneic marrow transplantation. *Blood.* 2000; 96(9): 3290–3293.
18. Asma GE, van den Bergh RL, Vossen JM. Regeneration of TdT+, pre-B, and B cells in bone marrow after allogeneic bone marrow transplantation. *Transplantation.* 1987; 43: 865-870.
19. Leitenberg D; Rappeport JM, Smith BR. B-cell precursor bone marrow reconstitution after bone marrow transplantation. *Am Clin Pathol.* 1994; 102(2):231-236.

20. Storek J, Wells D, Dawson MA, Storer B, Maloney DG. Factors influencing B lymphopoiesis after allogeneic hematopoietic cell transplantation. *Blood*. 2001; 98(2): 489-491.
21. Porata LF, Markovic SN. Timely reconstitution of immune competence affects clinical outcome following autologous stem cell transplantation. *Clin Exp Med*. 2004; 4: 78-85.
22. Powles R, Singhal S, Treleaven J, Kulkarni S, Horton C, Mehta J, et al. Identification of patients who benefit from prophylactic immunotherapy after bone marrow transplantation for acute myeloid leukemia on the basis of lymphocyte recovery early after transplantation. *Blood*. 1998; 91(9):3481-3486.
23. Pavletic ZS, Joshi SS, Pirruccello SJ, Tarantolo SR, Kollath J, Reed EC, et al. Lymphocyte reconstitution after allogeneic blood stem cell transplantation for hematologic malignancies. *Bone Marrow Transplant*. 1998; 21:33-41.
24. Kumar S, Chen MG, Gastineau DA, Gertz MA, Inwards DJ, Lacy MQ, et al. Lymphocyte recovery after allogeneic bone marrow transplantation predicts risk of relapse in acute lymphoblastic leukemia. *Leukemia*. 2003; 17:1865-1870.
25. Kim DH, Kim JG, Sohn SK, Sung WJ, Suh JS, Lee KS, et al. Clinical impact of early absolute lymphocyte count after allogeneic stem cell transplantation. *Br J Haematol*. 2004; 125(2):217-224.
26. Small TN, Papadopoulos EB, Boulad F, Black P, Castro-Malaspina H, Childs BH, et al. Comparison of immune reconstitution after unrelated and related T-cell depleted bone marrow transplantation: effect of patient age and donor leukocyte infusions. *Blood*. 1999; 93(2): 467-480.
27. Storek J, Dawson MA, Storer B, Stevens- Ayers T, Maloney DG, Marr KA, et al Immune reconstitution after allogeneic marrow transplantation compared with blood stem cell transplantation. *Blood*. 2001; 97(11): 3380-3389.
28. Cuvelier GD, Schutz KR, Davis J, Hirschfeld AF, Junker AK, Tan R, et al. Optimizing outcomes of hematopoietic stem cell transplantation for severe combined immunodeficiency. *Clin Immunol*. 2009;131(2): 179-188.
29. Nossal GJ. Negative selection of lymphocytes. *Cell*. 1994; 76:229-239.
30. Fry AM, Jones LA, Kruisbeck AM, Matis LA. Thymic requirement for clonal deletion during T cell development. *Science*. 1989; 246(4933):1044-1046.
31. Hodes RJ, Sharrow SO, Solomon A. Failure of T cell receptor V beta negative selection in a thymic environment. *Science*. 1989; 246:1041-1044.
32. Pizzo PA, Rubin M, Freifeld A, Walsh TJ. The child with cancer and infection: II. Nonbacterial infections. *J Pediatr*. 1991; 119(5): 845-857.
33. Mackall CL, Fleisher TA, Brown MR, Magrath IT, Shad AT, Horowitz ME, et al. Lymphocyte depletion during treatment with intensive chemotherapy for cancer. *Blood*. 1994; 84(7):2221-2228.
34. Mackall CL. T-cell immunodeficiency following cytotoxic antineoplastic therapy: a review. *Stem Cell*. 2000; 18:10-18.
35. Chakrabarti A, Brown J, Guttridge M, Pamphilon DH, Lankester A, Marks DI, et al. Early lymphocyte recovery is an important determinant of outcome following allogeneic transplantation with CD34+ selected graft and limited T-cell add-back. *Bone marrow Transplant*. 2003; 32(1):23-30.
36. Remberger M, Ringden O, Blau IW, Ottinger H, Kremens B, Kiehl MG, et al. No difference in graft-versus-host disease, relapse, and survival comparing peripheral stem cells to bone marrow using unrelated donors. *Blood*. 2001; 98(6):1739-1745.
37. Fries BC, Khaira D, Pepe MS, Torok-Storb B. Declining lymphocyte counts following cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection are associated with fatal CMV disease in bone marrow transplant patients. *Exp Hematol*. 1993; 21: 1387-1392.